

Determinants of Possible Growth of Longganisa Businesses in Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija

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Abstract:- Cabanatuan's longganisa today have been becoming popular across the region, to improve the marketing strategies, production, management, and cooperation among business owners of longganisa products is through implementing new holistic business strategies. This research aimed to find out how longganisa entrepreneurs in Cabanatuan City used the concept of cooperation, and examined its significant impact on their present undertakings. Furthermore, this research analyzed the contribution of the establishment of cooperative among the vendors of longganisa with the support of the Cabanatuan City local government, which may possibly improve the livelihood of our small business owners of longganisa. The respondents of the study were the twenty (20) registered owners of longganisa business in Cabanatuan City. The researcher used a questionnaire checklist for collecting the data which measured different variables such as the capital of the business, marketing knowledge, the reasons patronizing their longganisa and challenges encountered which are all related to running a longganisa business.

Keywords:- Longganisa, Longganisa Business, Cooperative, Challenges.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cabanatuan is generally recognized for their longganisa products and it is most known for the origin of Batutay - a beef based longganisa with a sweet flavor. Compared to other Philippine longganisas, the Cabanatuan longganisa is chunkier with larger bits of meat and garlic in every bite.

Among the fresh processed meats, longganisa is the most frequently purchased pork product, which is known to be a Filipino version of hotdog. Any part of a pork carcass like ham (pigue), shoulder (kasim), loin (lomo), and others, except the belly (liempo), can be made into longganisa. Cabanatuan longganisa, also known as batutay, is a Filipino beef sausage originated from Cabanatuan City, Nueva Ecija. It can be served sweet (*hamonado*), garlicky (*de recado*), or "skinless" (without the casing). It is celebrated in the annual "Longganisa Festival" of Cabanatuan City.

This study aimed to find out how longganisa business in Cabanatuan City should be used the concept of uniqueness and affordability of its worth and the impact in the livelihood of the small owners of longganisa entrepreneurs present undertakings. Furthermore, this research analyzed the best marketing strategies being used in order to improve the present standard of quality of the Cabanatuan longganisa products and noted the challenges tied in the implementation of such new strategies.

The researcher also perceived that business owners handling meat processing products have encountered African Swine Fever or ASF, which brought a scare to a lot of customers in Cabanatuan City causing a low market on Meat Products specially longganisa which is very popular in Cabanatuan City. According to Rappler-Ralf Rivas, "the National Meat Inspection Service (NMIS), ASF is a highly contagious viral disease that affects pigs, warthogs, and boars. It causes pigs to have a high fever and lose their appetite. It also causes hemorrhages in the skin and internal organs. Death is certain, pigs die in a span of 2 to 10 days upon affliction. There is no known vaccine against ASF yet.

The outcome of this study may encourage the longganisa business owners to unite and cooperate to give an idea for improving their longganisa products as with a remarkable taste among other longganisa around the region. Best strategies which will give them a way to be better and more effective in promoting their products across the nation or even abroad. This study demonstrates that the longganisa business is an important player in the Cabanatuan economy and should be promoted as one of Cabanatuan's specialty products.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study aimed to evaluate the Determinants of Possible Growth of Longganisa Business in Cabanatuan City.

Specifically, it answers the following questions:

- What new business strategies they should use in order to expand and improve the longganisa industry in Cabanatuan City?
- What are the reasons why Cabanatuan longganisa well patronized by consumers or "suki" across the region?
- What are the challenges faced by the longganisa business owners in selling their products?

III. METHODOLOGY

The respondents of the study were the 20 registered owners of selected longganisa business owners in Cabanatuan City. They were tasked to assess their possible growth in this business.

The questionnaire was the main instrument used by the researcher in conducting this study. A structured questionnaire and a five-point likert scale for assessing the determinants of possible growth of longganisa businesses were utilized.

Table 1: Response Mode

Rank	Reasons for Using New Business Strategies in Longganisa Business, Benefits and Challenges	Possible Growth of Longganisa Business
5	Strongly Agree	Always
4	Agree	Often
3	Moderately Agree	Sometimes
2	Disagree	Seldom
1	Strongly Disagree	Never

Table 2: Scoring

Ranges	Reasons for Using New Business Strategies in Longganisa Business, Benefits and Challenges	Possible Growth of Longganisa Business
4.21- 5.00	Strongly Agree	Always
3.41-4.20	Agree	Often
2.61-3.40	Moderately Agree	Sometimes
1.81-2.60	Disagree	Seldom
1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Never

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter provides the presentation of data relevant to the problems stated in Chapter 1. Corresponding analysis and interpretation were discussed using some statistical tools.

A. Reasons for adopting new business strategies

Table 1 presents the reasons why the longganisa business in Cabanatuan City are now adopting new business strategies.

Table 3 Reasons for Adopting New Business Strategies

Reasons	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Opportunities or competitive advantage	4.35	Agree
2. Increase business value and profitability	4.35	Strongly Agree
3. Local Government initiative	3.90	Agree
4. Competitive pressure	3.90	Agree
5. Cost Leadership	3.55	Agree
Gen. Weighted Mean	4.01	Agree

Item 1 & 2 got the weighted mean of 4.35 and the top reason for having a lot of opportunities or competitive advantage and adopting new business strategies of their products. Longganisa business owners believed that they have an obligation to increase productivity. Meanwhile, item 1 got a weighted mean of 4.20. This denotes that longganisa business owners wanted to also take the opportunities on the competitive advantage. Longganisa business owners perceived strategic alliances as an opportunity that can be used to achieve its objectives.

On the other hand, items 3 and 4 got a weighted mean of 3.90. This implies that longganisa business owners do adopt new business strategies because of government pressure and competitive pressure. Government encourages that the longganisa industry in Cabanatuan City has the potential to get the higher market impact outside Cabanatuan and to use new business strategies same as with competitors in other provinces, and pressure them to adopt new business strategies. Lastly, item 5 got a weighted mean of 3.55 which implies that cost leadership or the most competitively priced product on the market must be imposed.

B. Benefits of New Business Strategies

Table 2 presents the benefits of new marketing as perceived by the owners of longganisa business in Cabanatuan City.

Table 4 Benefits of Developing New Business Strategies

Benefits	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Establishing long term direction through cooperative.	4.34	Strongly Agree
2. It helps to improve the livelihood of the longganisa business owners.	4.30	Strongly Agree
3. Standardize the quality of Cabanatuan longganisa products to be well known across the region.	4.34	Strongly Agree
4. Can gain public approval and satisfy the buyers to continuing patronising the Cabanatuan longganisa products.	4.30	Strongly Agree
5. It helps in enjoying competitive advantage.	4.55	Strongly Agree
6. Promoting effectively the Cabanatuan longganisa can acquire a greater market share.	4.42	Strongly Agree
7. Improving longganisa products and apply best	4.34	Strongly Agree

practices in overall aspects can attract new customers.		
8. Portraying a common friendly business image through cooperative among longganisa business owners and sales promotion can keep loyal customers groups.	4.47	Strongly Agree
9. Using holistic approach for positive positioning can project a corporate social responsibility image.	4.36	Strongly Agree
General Weighted Mean	4.38	Strongly Agree

Item 5 got a weighted mean of 4.55 and was ranked first among the benefits of new business strategies. This denotes that new business strategies helped longganisa business owners in enjoying competitive advantage.

Meanwhile, item 8 got a weighted mean of 4.47 which implies that longganisa business owners can portray a very cooperative image through advertising and sales promotion which can keep a group of loyal customers. Item 6 got a weighted mean of 4.42 which denotes that the longganisa business owners can acquire a greater market share through new business strategies.

On the other hand, items 1, 3, 7 and 9 got a weighted mean of 4.34. This implies that longganisa business owners can enhance their products with a holistic approach among other longganisa vendors and can obtain a long-term good reputation. In addition, the use of new business strategies can maintain and improve the recognition of Cabanatuan longganisa across the country and even abroad.

Lastly, items 2 and 4 got a weighted mean of 4.30 which denotes that the use of new business strategies can improve livelihood of the longganisa business owners, attract new customers, and can gain public approval and possibility of recognizing their products in the long term.

C. New marketing strategies used by longganisa business owners in Cabanatuan City.

Table 3 presents the new marketing strategies used by longganisa business owners in Cabanatuan City.

Table 5 Strategies used by Longganisa Business Owners in Cabanatuan City

Strategies	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Using high quality uniform ingredients of their longganisa products through cooperative.	4.37	Always
2. Consistency in the quality of longganisa	4.37	Always
3. Giving discount to wholesalers/suki	3.58	Sometimes
4. Using clean pork intestine.	4.06	Often
5. Giving freebies to promote the longganisa products to another province	3.48	Often
6. Giving of eco bags for free	3.41	Sometimes
7. Maintaining proper hygiene	4.23	Often
8. Serves proper portion of meat to reduce food waste	3.87	Often
9. Using attractive product label	3.87	Often
Gen. Weighted Mean	3.92	Often

Strategies 1 and 2 got a weighted mean of 4.37 which denotes that longganisa business owners implemented the consistency of the quality of their products among other vendors of longganisa in Cabanatuan City.

Strategy number 7 got a weighted mean of 4.23 which implies that longganisa business owners should maintain the proper hygiene in handling their products.

Meanwhile, strategy number 4 got a weighted mean of 4.06. This denotes a cleaned and quality-controlled pork intestine. Strategies 8 and 9 got a weighted mean of 3.87 which implies that the top green marketing strategies used by restaurant owners/managers were the non-smoking policy and placing of green live plants for indoor air quality.

Lastly, strategies 3, 5 and 6 got a weighted mean of 3.58, 3.48, and 3.41, respectively. This implies that the longganisa business owners also considered giving discounts to suki and wholesalers, giving freebies, and giving eco bags.

D. Challenges faced by the longganisa business owners in implementing new strategies.

Table 4 presents the challenges faced by the longganisa business owners in Cabanatuan City in implementing new business strategies.

Items 1, 2, 6 and 8 got a weighted mean of 4.36. This implies that the main challenges of longganisa business were: majority of the longganisa vendors were not aware of the benefits of cooperation among vendors of Cabanatuan longganisa; products' remarkable packaging require of Cabanatuan specialty in longganisa; no comprehensive support from the authority when there was an African Swine Flu also affected the supply and production of longganisa.

Meanwhile, item 4 got a weighted mean of 4.28 which implies that some customers encountered damaged of their products during the travel from the market going to their destinations. Item 3 and 5 got a weighted mean of 4.15 which denotes that since longganisa came from pork they believe it is an unhealthy fatty food and lastly the unexpected bulk orders of longganisa make it hard for business owners to turn down the demand in order to maintain the loyalty of their customers.

Table 6 Challenges Faced by the Longganisa Business Owners in Implementing New Business Strategies

Challenges	Weighted Mean	Description
1. Convincing other longganisa vendors to form cooperative.	4.36	Strongly Agree
2. Products' packaging requires an attractive and unique label which are expensive.	4.36	Strongly Agree
3. People are often perceived that longganisa is fatty foods and unhealthy.	4.15	Agree
4. The damaged sometimes done by the buyers during the long travel of transporting the products.	4.28	Strongly Agree
5. Unscheduled bulk orders sometimes by the buyers.	4.15	Agree
6. African Swine Flu (ASF) affected the supply of pork.	4.36	Strongly Agree
7. Increasing number of competitors in different provinces.	4.07	Agree
8. Inconsistency of the implementation of government support fund for the meat processing business owners during the ASF contagious viral disease.	4.36	Strongly Agree
Gen. Weighted Mean	4.26	Strongly Agree

Lastly, item number 7 got a weighted mean of 4.07 which denotes that increasing number of competitors is another challenge in using new business strategies.

V. CONCLUSIONS

As to the reasons for adopting a holistic approach of longganisa business owners, they were motivated to use the new business strategy to show their cooperation and established a long-term recognition of the finest Cabanatuan longganisa. Longganisa business owners believed that they have a big chance to improve their lives once it is implemented.

As to the cooperative and applying new business strategies, it helped longganisa business owners in accessing the new markets and enjoying competitive advantage.

As to new business strategies, longganisa business owners use high-quality ingredients, maintain proper hygiene and consistency of Cabanatuan longganisa, attracts more customers, helps the industry, and supports from the local government one way or another.

As to the challenges of longganisa business owners the main challenges of improving the business strategies were: the implementation of cooperative among longganisa business owners, products' packaging requiring remarkable but inexpensive; no concrete government support plan; and inconsistency of the product quality of Cabanatuans' longganisa.

As to the coping mechanisms, the main coping mechanism of longganisa business owners towards the challenges of new business strategies was the use of holistic approach among longganisa vendors in Cabanatuan City through the implementation of Cooperative.

Based from the results of the study, the researcher arrived at the following conclusions:

- Longganisa business owners in Cabanatuan City were motivated by new business strategies to expand their longganisa business and long-term benefit.
- Number one benefit of the new business strategy was to gain a competitive advantage over its competitors.
- Top business marketing strategies used by the longganisa business owners were the implementation of cooperation among vendors of longganisa in Cabanatuan City.
- Top challenges encountered by the longganisa business owners in implementing new business strategies were primarily on the training/seminars cost involved in establishment of a cooperative.
- Coping mechanisms of longganisa business owners towards the challenges of establishment of a cooperative was the help of the local government in this project.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are offered:

- Longganisa business owners should have a new business plan in integrating the holistic expansion and innovation of products.
- The owners of longganisa business in Cabanatuan City should establish a cooperative for the effectiveness of their new business strategies.
- Another study prior to the effectiveness of longganisa business strategies in Cabanatuan City should be conducted.
- Implementation of high-quality longganisa products and to form longganisa business owners cooperative market association among Cabanartuan City meat vendors.

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